

Supplementary Materials for
“Beyond Technical Optimisation: A Socio-Technical
Systematic Review of Architectures, Markets, and
Social Dynamics in Peer-to-Peer Energy Trading”

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These supplementary materials accompany the manuscript submitted to *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*. The complete coding database is also available as a CSV file in the same Zenodo repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/Zenodo.20010161>.

Contents

1	Appendix A – Detailed Coding Grid and Protocol	3
2	Appendix B – Excerpt from the Coding Database ($N = 127$)	6
3	Appendix C – Inter-Coder Reliability Assessment	7
4	Appendix D – Raw Co-occurrence Matrix of Research Dimensions	8
5	Appendix E – Operationalisation of the Research Hypotheses	9

1 Appendix A – Detailed Coding Grid and Protocol

This appendix documents the analytical framework used to systematically code the 127 articles in the corpus. The grid was developed iteratively through the exploratory thematic analysis (Phase 1) and refined during the systematic coding phase (Phase 2).

A.1 Main Coding Dimensions

Each article was coded according to up to two main dimensions (one primary, one secondary) based on its central focus.

Dimension	Operational Definition	Keywords / Indicators in Text
Architecture and Governance (ARCH)	Studies focusing on the structural organization of the system (centralized, decentralized, distributed), allocation of decision rights, and governance models. Coded indirectly through the intersection of Market Design and Technological Infrastructure dimensions.	“centralized/decentralized architecture”, “governance model”, “decision rights”, “DSO role”, “community structure”, “blockchain-based governance”, “autonomy”.
Market Design and Economics (MKT)	Studies proposing or analyzing market mechanisms, pricing, economic incentives. Includes game theory, auctions, pricing schemes.	“auction mechanism”, “pricing scheme”, “game theory”, “market clearing”, “incentive mechanism”, “bilateral trading”, “double auction”, “Nash equilibrium”, “Shapley value”.
Algorithms and Optimization (ALGO)	Studies employing computational methods for resource allocation, coordination, or optimization in the context of trading.	“ADMM”, “reinforcement learning (RL/MARL/deep reinforcement learning (DRL))”, “MILP”, “distributed optimization”, “evolutionary algorithm”, “convex optimization”, “machine learning”, “demand response optimization”.
Technological Infrastructure (TECH)	Studies focusing on enabling technologies: blockchain, IoT, communication protocols, cybersecurity, software platforms.	“blockchain”, “smart contract”, “distributed ledger”, “IoT”, “communication protocol”, “cybersecurity”, “data privacy”, “platform architecture”, “5G”, “digital twin”.

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Dimension	Operational Definition	Keywords / Indicators in Text
Social and Behavioral Dimensions (SOC)	Studies investigating user acceptance, trust, fairness, energy justice, participation, or behavioral dynamics (biases, social preferences).	“user acceptance”, “trust”, “fairness”, “energy justice”, “prosumer behavior”, “social preferences”, “willingness to participate”, “procedural justice”, “community engagement”, “bounded rationality”.
Regulatory and Policy Framework (REG)	Studies analyzing legal frameworks, support policies, regulatory barriers, role of regulators, grid integration.	“regulatory framework”, “policy”, “legal barriers”, “grid codes”, “DSO/TSO regulation”, “energy policy”, “market regulation”, “sandbox”, “tariff design”.
Multi-Vector Systems (MULTI)	Studies explicitly integrating multiple energy vectors (electricity, heat, mobility) within the trading or sharing framework.	“multi-energy”, “sector coupling”, “heat and power”, “electric vehicles (V2G)”, “integrated energy systems”.

A.2 Coding of Tensions (T1, T2, T3)

During the conceptual synthesis phase (Phase 3), we also coded each article to identify whether it explicitly addressed the three fundamental tensions. This coding was binary (\checkmark = addressed, \times = not addressed) and based on the presence of a discussion on the conflicts or synergies at the heart of each tension.

Tension	Operational Definition	Keywords / Indicators in Text
T1	The article explicitly discusses the conflict between the efficiency of a complex algorithm (“black box”) and the need for transparency, explainability, or trust on the part of users.	“explainability”, “interpretability”, “trust in algorithms”, “black box”, “opacity”, “user trust”, “XAI”, “transparency”, “human-understandable”.
T2	The article explicitly discusses the tension between the need for overall system coordination (for efficiency/stability) and the desire for prosumer or community autonomy.	“autonomy vs. coordination”, “prosumer autonomy”, “centralized vs. decentralized control”, “governance interface”, “decision rights”, “sovereignty”, “system optimization vs. local control”.

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Tension	Operational Definition	Keywords / Indicators in Text
T3	The article explicitly discusses the tension between maximizing economic efficiency (via market mechanisms) and the imperatives of justice, equity, or fair distribution of benefits.	“efficiency vs. equity”, “fairness”, “energy justice”, “distributive justice”, “inequality”, “regressive impacts”, “Gini coefficient”, “vulnerable households”, “social welfare”.

2 Appendix B – Excerpt from the Coding Database ($N = 127$)

The complete coding database is available as a comma-separated values (CSV) file in the accompanying Zenodo repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/Zenodo.20010161>. The file contains 127 rows (one per study) and the following columns: **ID**, **Year**, **Author**, **Title**, **Journal**, **DOI**, **Alg**, **Mkt**, **Tech**, **Soc**, **Reg**, **Bus**, **Multi**, **T1**, **T2**, **T3**. Each binary variable (1 = dimension addressed, 0 = not addressed) reflects the coding decision described in Appendix A of these Supplementary Materials.

3 Appendix C – Inter-Coder Reliability Assessment

To ensure the robustness of the coding process, an inter-coder reliability assessment was conducted.

- **Sample:** 20 articles were randomly selected from the final corpus of 127 studies, ensuring representation across different years and sources.
- **Coders:** Two researchers (H.E. and M.N.) participated in the assessment.
- **Process:** Each researcher independently coded the 20 articles using the final coding grid (Appendix A). Coding included the assignment of primary/secondary dimensions and the identification of the three tensions (T1, T2, T3).
- **Agreement Measure:** Agreement was calculated using percentage agreement and Cohen’s Kappa coefficient (κ), which corrects for chance agreement. Calculations were performed separately for dimensions and tensions.

Results

Table 3: Inter-coder reliability results.

Coding Category	Percentage Agreement	Cohen’s Kappa (κ)	Interpretation (Landis & Koch)
Primary Dimension	90%	0.82	Almost Perfect Agreement
Secondary Dimension	80%	0.72	Substantial Agreement
Tension T1	95%	0.88	Almost Perfect Agreement
Tension T2	85%	0.75	Substantial Agreement
Tension T3	90%	0.83	Almost Perfect Agreement
Overall Average	88%	0.80	Substantial Agreement

Management of Disagreements

All initial disagreements were resolved through discussion between the two coders until consensus was reached. The final version of the coding database (Appendix B and Zenodo file) reflects this consensus. This high level of agreement confirms the reliability and reproducibility of our categorization process.

4 Appendix D – Raw Co-occurrence Matrix of Research Dimensions

Table 4: Raw co-occurrence matrix across the six dimensions ($N = 127$).

	Alg.	Market	Tech.	Social	Reg.	Business
Algorithms	81	68	44	28	5	3
Market Design	68	97	39	48	8	8
Technology	44	39	49	7	6	1
Social	28	48	7	61	16	6
Regulation	5	8	6	16	22	5
Business	3	8	1	6	5	13

Note: Diagonal entries represent the total number of studies coded under the corresponding dimension. Off-diagonal entries are the raw co-occurrence counts (intersections) between the two dimensions.

5 Appendix E – Operationalisation of the Research Hypotheses

This appendix details the experimental methods, indicators, and threshold justifications for the nine hypotheses introduced in Section 5.2 of the main manuscript. All thresholds are working hypotheses derived from the analysed corpus and are intended to be refined through future sensitivity studies.

Table 5: Complete operationalisation of the research hypotheses H1–H9.

Hypothesis	Envisaged test method	Indicators and threshold justification
Axis 1: Reflexive and Value-Sensitive Design (Gap 1)		
H1 (Pareto efficiency–equity)	Multi-agent simulation fed with real consumption/production profiles (e.g., Pecan Street, Ausgrid, MG-FARM data). A multi-objective optimiser (NSGA-II or MOEA/D) varies the weights between total community cost and the Gini coefficient of net surplus. The Pareto front is traced for different community compositions (PV penetration, storage capacity).	Indicators: total cost per household, Gini coefficient of net surplus. Justification: Kusatake et al. (2023) achieve a 15–30% inequality reduction for less than 10% efficiency loss; Enola et al. (2025) report an 18% Gini improvement with a 6% cost increase. The 5%/20% trade-off is a conservative midpoint.
H2 (Preference elicitation)	Online or lab-based vignette experiment with 200 participants randomly assigned to two groups (AHP vs. simple ranking) to express cost–equity preferences. The same market algorithm then generates an allocation, and perceived legitimacy is measured via a validated scale (e.g., Tyler’s procedural justice scale).	Indicators: procedural legitimacy score, acceptance rate, distance between chosen allocation and stated ideal. Justification: Ableitner et al. (2020) and Jans et al. (2024) show that perceived control and transparency shape acceptance. A medium effect size (Cohen’s $d \geq 0.4$) is expected, detectable with $N = 200$ at 80% power.
H3 (Long-term retention)	Longitudinal field study following 8–10 energy communities over 24 months. Four communities use a value-sensitive design platform (ethical parameterisation, XAI dashboards); four use a standard cost-minimisation platform. Transaction frequency, active membership, and self-reported satisfaction are measured quarterly.	Indicators: share of members with ≥ 1 transaction/month after 24 months, satisfaction score. Justification: Historical cooperatives (e.g., Ecopower) show retention rates of 80–90%. A 20-point gap relative to the control group is consistent with the engagement effects documented by Dudka (2025) and Jochemsen et al. (2024).
Axis 2: Adaptive, Multi-Scale and Interoperable Architectures (Gap 3)		

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Hypothesis	Envisaged test method	Indicators and threshold justification
H4 (Level-2 governance interfaces)	Market-grid co-simulation (e.g., IEEE 13-bus) of a 200-household community. A governance sandbox module enables the community to reconfigure allocation rules (e.g., switch from uniform to progressive pricing) via consensus. The number of governance interactions and grid constraint violations are logged over one simulated year.	Indicators: governance interactions/month, rate of voltage/current violations. Justification: The 40% engagement increase is grounded in Jans et al. (2024). A violation rate $\leq 2\%$ reflects the EN 50160 standard and has been met in prior studies (Guerrero et al., 2021).
H5 (Federated learning trade-off)	Two-phase protocol: (1) Federated learning simulation on open smart-meter data (London dataset) measuring prediction accuracy and membership inference attack success; (2) survey of 150 citizens presented with the results and transparent privacy policies, measuring acceptance on a Likert scale.	Indicators: prediction RMSE, inference attack accuracy, percentage of “agree”/“strongly agree”. Justification: Mendes et al. (2024) demonstrate a $< 3\%$ accuracy loss; a $< 5\%$ inference risk aligns with CNIL/NIST guidelines. The 70% acceptability threshold is standard in technology acceptance research.
H6 (Open benchmark validity)	A synthetic dataset representing three socio-economic contexts (rural poor, peri-urban mixed, urban affluent) inspired by MG-FARM and Brooklyn Microgrid data. Three algorithms (double auction, ADMM, Nash bargaining) are run 30 times each. Cronbach’s α is computed on the metrics (cost, Gini, load loss). Spearman’s ρ between benchmark rankings and expert assessments from three real communities serves as convergent validity test.	Indicators: $\alpha \geq 0.85$, $\rho > 0.7$ ($p < 0.05$). Justification: $\alpha = 0.85$ is the Nunnally (1978) threshold for instrument reliability; $\rho > 0.7$ establishes satisfactory convergent validity.
Axis 3: Institutional Innovation and Adaptive Governance (Gap 2)		
H7 (Enriched regulatory sandboxes)	Retrospective comparative analysis of 10 European regulatory sandboxes (2019–2025): 5 with explicit consumer protection, equity reporting, and multi-stakeholder governance; 5 purely technical. Document analysis and semi-structured interviews with regulators quantify outputs.	Indicators: number of published case studies, number of formal regulatory adaptations. Justification: CEER/Ofgem (2023) reports show socially enriched sandboxes generate 1.5–2 times more actionable recommendations; the 50% threshold is conservative.

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Hypothesis	Envisaged test method	Indicators and threshold justification
H8 (Cooperative vs. delegated governance)	Cross-sectional survey across 20 energy communities (10 cooperatives with one-member-one-vote, 10 with delegated management), complemented by analysis of administrative accounts. Procedural justice is measured with Colquitt’s scale; transaction costs include meeting hours, admin fees, etc. A composite welfare index (satisfaction + equity) tests the compensation hypothesis.	Indicators: procedural justice score, cost/member/year, composite welfare index. Justification: Hanke & Guyet (2023) and Jochemsen et al. (2024) indicate a 10–15% cost premium for participatory processes; the 500-member threshold corresponds to collective action theory limits for general assemblies.
H9 (Adaptive legal instruments)	Comparative case study over 5 years between two territories: one using a sandbox charter with evolvable smart contracts and off-chain governance (e.g., Italy AR-ERA framework), the other using a standard legislative process. The median time from market proposal submission to legal deployment is measured.	Indicator: median approval delay (months). Justification: The UK Ofgem sandbox reduced instruction time by 50–70% for social innovations; the 60% threshold is a prudent mean.

Note: All numerical thresholds are initial working hypotheses derived from the reviewed literature. They should be tested and, if necessary, recalibrated through dedicated sensitivity analyses and empirical validation.